

Indigenous Traditional Knowledge and its Preservation: A Study on the Jewellery Industry of Ranthali, Assam

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In every society, Indigenous people and local communities embrace a unique place because of their distinct tradition and cultural identities. Indigenous Traditional Knowledge is based on people's many years of experimentation on their available surroundings and their experiences in dealing with various problems of their lives. The World Health Organization has stated that 80 percent of the world's population still depends on their traditional medicine for its primary health care and Traditional Knowledge is indispensable for its survival. Traditional knowledge has helped in creating a self-reliant economy in indigenous societies from a very long time. For example, indigenous societies have the traditional knowledge of producing unique clothing, food items, utensils, medicines from locally available resources. But from the past two decades the search for an appropriate mechanism to protect these Traditional Knowledge of Indigenous people has been a subject of discussion among many international policy agents, environmentalist and indigenous-rights activists. Intellectual Property Rights as a mechanism for the protection of these traditional knowledge has become a key concern. These developments in international law to protect knowledge of indigenous people indicates the necessity of its preservation. Besides these, there are many Traditional experts on distinctive areas, the valuable knowledge of whom are still hidden and unknown to the rest of the world. The protection of the identity of the Traditional Experts can become the first step to protect the valuable Traditional Knowledge, so that it can flow from generation to generation without any misconception. This study is an attempt to understand the traditional jewellery making industry of Ranthali, Assam and the need of protecting this industry from the rapidly growing industrialization in this globalized era.

Keywords: Traditional Knowledge, Indigenous, Intellectual Property Rights, Economy, Assamese Jewellery